

A Postcolonial Ecocritical Study of African Dystopian Climate Fiction: *It Doesn't Have to Be This Way*

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Abstract: *This study aims to comprehend why environmental activism in African literature is represented as a failed attempt to resist the perpetuation of climate criminality. Through textual analysis of the South African author Alistair Mackay's dystopian climate fiction, It Doesn't Have to Be This Way (2022), this paper challenges the conceptual frameworks that portray indigenous environmentalism as anti-nationalist. Mackay's novel illustrates how political indifference escalates the pursuit of climate justice into radical and even violent forms of resistance. Drawing on postcolonial ecocriticism, this paper elucidates how the Western model of development establishes itself as a form of neocolonialism across the political and environmental landscape of the non-Western world. In Mackay's novel, South Africa is represented as a bifurcated nation caught between two conflicting material and ideological trajectories: developmentalism and environmentalism. In the story, Luthando, a black African man of queer identity, protests against the Western capitalist system for accelerating the climate crisis, but he encounters opposition from pro-industrial Africans. This articulates how environmental attitudes in postcolonial countries are shaped by what the postcolonial critic Homi K. Bhabha has termed 'ambivalence'. Analysing the ambivalent responses to ecological issues, this study will emphasise the central question of why ambivalence is significant for speculating about a sustainable future. This study will investigate whether climate fiction serves any environmental purpose or merely functions as propaganda for Western*

ideologies. Moreover, the integration of the dystopian element in the story will be analysed as a mode of satire against the Western heteronormative religious and capitalist practices. It will examine how these Western ideological apparatuses exacerbate the identity crisis of queer people in a climatically post-apocalyptic world.

Keywords: Ambivalence, Climate fiction, Development, Postcolonial ecocriticism, Resistance.

Introduction: Development in Postcolonial Ecocriticism

The representation of environmental issues in postcolonial literature plays a crucial role in developing an understanding of the human-nature relationship. A sense of resistance against the oppressive political ideologies of Western society constitutes an important element of the mainstream literature of postcolonial nations. These political ideas refer to a set of beliefs that have perpetuated and historically legitimised Western dominance over the colonised countries. Notably, the colonial expansion was exploitative not only for the colonised people but also for the ecological system of their nations. This indicates that Western ideological frameworks are shaped by colonialism and capitalist expansion. In this sense, the resistance to the violence of colonialism is also a resistance to the ecological exploitation of capitalism.

One of the primary goals of postcolonial ecocriticism is to analyse in depth the Western framework of development. Western developmental ideals perpetuate colonial patterns of dominance through the exploitation of natural resources, the marginalisation of indigenous knowledge, and the strengthening of the Eastern countries' financial dependence on the West. Graham Huggan and Helen Tiffin analyse Western developmental ideologies as “a disguised form of neocolonialism” (29). These postcolonial critics argue that Western ideologies of development function as a “technocratic apparatus to serve the economic and political interests of the West” (29). By using cultural hegemony, environmental regulations, and economic pressure, Western

nations exploit developmental strategy as a tool of neocolonialism to maintain the legacy of colonial authority over the postcolonial nations.

It is widely acknowledged that the term ‘development’ is strategically ambiguous, customised to the many demands of its users, and grounded in the vast cultural presumptions and assumptions of the West (Black 3). Similarly, the German sociologist Wolfgang Sachs argues that the concept of development is shaped by its relation to the economies of First World nations. He points out that “what development means depends on how the rich nations feel” (Sachs26). In fact, development is “a form of strategic altruism” designed to serve the political and economic interests of developed countries of the West (Huggan and Tiffin 30). These developed countries function as neocolonial agents to dominate the geopolitical and economic conditions of postcolonial developing nations.

Hence, it is legitimate points to make that the development theories have an intimate connection with the false promises of the colonial masters who started their colonial enterprise with the mission of civilising the people of the colonised nations. Oswaldo De Rivero, a Peruvian diplomat who served as Ambassador to the United States, contends that development is essentially a myth promoted by the West (110). It re-establishes the social, political, and economic divide between the First and Third World nations that it falsely seeks to bridge under the pretence of modernisation. He emphatically asserts that this development myth encourages less-developed nations of the Global South to emulate their wealthier northern counterparts. Imitation of the Western model of development compels non-Western countries to adopt a capitalist model that is both blatantly unjust and environmentally disastrous (De Rivero 110).

This Western model of development perpetuates Western dominance by categorising ‘developed’ and ‘underdeveloped’ nations in ways that exacerbate structural inequalities. Moreover, the West’s development narrative is both an economic framework

and a hegemonic tool. It consolidates the West's social, cultural, and political authority over postcolonial nations by shaping their aspirations, policies, and socioeconomic structures in accordance with dominant Western paradigms. Western dominance over the East's economic and political conditions deepens the gap between the rich and the poor. This creates a modern form of "socio-economic apartheid: a planet in whose northern hemisphere there is a small archipelago of wealthy nation-states, surrounded by the majority of mankind" (De Rivero24). This demonstrates that development functions both as an agent of economic management and a technique of discursive control.

Western Development Ideology and the Inequal Economic Structure:

Mackay's *It Doesn't Have to Be This Way* is set in a fictional town named Kapelitsha Island, which resembles Khayelitsha, Cape Town's largest informal settlement. This fictional township is depicted as nearly uninhabitable: water has run out; oceans have risen and engulfed the coastal regions, and the unbearable temperature controls the slum outside "The Wall", which has separated the economically and politically influential people from the poorer section of society. The affluent people have either taken refuge in "The Citadel, a heavily guarded climate-controlled dome city on Signal Hill or migrated to "the New Temperate Zones, countries like Greenland, and "the northern reaches of Canada, Alaska, Norway" (Mackay195). Mackay has portrayed South Africa in ways that explain how postcolonial nations mimicked Western patterns of development. This also demonstrates how the theoretical praxes of development have generated an unequal economic structure not only between the West and the East but also within the periphery of postcolonial nations.

Nonetheless, the mimicry of Western socioeconomic and cultural practices has made it difficult for people in postcolonial nations to comprehend the underlying discursive motives of Western developmental theory. Development serves as a self-

servicing rhetoric of neocolonialism, as it is practised by individuals and institutions whose primary goal is to exploit others under the guise of social uplift. (Black 268). In Mackay's novel, the indigenous people, like Andile, are portrayed as victims of transnational corporate capitalist development. Andile is from the rural region Wild Coast, which he has to leave because "[i]t wasn't safe for [him] any longer" (Mackay95). What these multinational companies call developments have exacerbated the precarity for the indigenous people by rendering the local environment fragile and toxic. So, what is development for these companies is, in reality, an exploitation for both the environment and indigenous people.

Therefore, it is possible to argue that rather than abolishing Western imperial practices, modern development ideologies uphold them through partnerships between postcolonial governments and multinational corporations (Esteva 9-11). In the novel, Andile says:

We don't want to be poisoned. We don't want our cattle to die. We know [big corporates] put all kinds of chemicals into the soil. We don't want people to get sick, we said, it didn't matter. The mine makes money, so the mine went ahead. We lost. (Mackay95)

This elucidates how the Western capitalist mode of production is supported by the governments of postcolonial nations, which prioritise development over ecological sustainability. This is why indigenous environmental activism is considered antithetical to national development. In the novel, the representation of the indigenous community's failure to draw the government's attention to ecological disruption accelerated by the capitalist mode of production illustrates the ambivalent attitude that Western development ideology inculcates in the minds of postcolonial people. The concept of 'ambivalence' is developed by Homi. K. Bhabha employs it to describe "a process of disavowal" inherent in the relationship between the coloniser and the colonised (122). The relationship between the coloniser and the colonized is ambivalent,

marked by both repulsion and attraction toward the coloniser's hegemonic culture (Ashcroft et al. 13). On the one hand, the colonised oppose the imperial practices of their colonial masters. On the other hand, they mimic colonial ideologies to get out of the oppressive domain of colonialisation. Thus, they are always in an in-between space that heightens their ambivalence toward colonial culture.

In Mackay's *It Doesn't Have to Be This Way*, the clash between environmental activists and counter-protestors best illustrates this postcolonial ambivalence towards Western development ideology. The black African environmental activists protest against the multinational corporations whose exploitative activities exacerbate the planetary crisis of climate change. Nevertheless, they confront counter-protestors whose focus is not on environmental sustainability but economic development. For them, climate change is not "a real Problem" (Mackay70). Their real problem is financial insecurity. They are ready to follow the Western patterns of development to deal with this material crisis: "Environmental Protections Kill Jobs! ... We Want Housing! Re-Industrialisation=The Future. Open the Economy! The West Got Rich This Way, Now It's Our Turn" (70). People in developing countries in the Global South are most vulnerable to environmental crises, and their precarity is either a direct or an indirect result of the capitalist economies of First World countries, which encourage the commodification of natural resources.

Ambivalent Attitude Towards Environmental Catastrophe:

The impact of environmental vulnerability is not experienced equally by people in developing countries. The disproportionate effects of climate change and other environmental crises are a crucial factor in fostering ambivalence toward ecological sustainability. People from unstable financial backgrounds, such as Luthando or Andile, whose lives have been directly affected by environmental collapse, have a different experience from those who are economically dominant and politically powerful, such as the president or the counter-protestors

in the novel. Indigenous peoples' firsthand knowledge of the catastrophic impacts of climate change prompts them to organise protests against government-aided transnational corporations. Their environmental campaign aims to prioritise ecological sustainability in modern development. Several questions emerge that problematize the relationship between development and sustainability: Is it possible to imagine sustainability without development? Could humanity survive an environmental catastrophe without economic development? However, does economic development really ensure a sustainable future?

In postcolonial ecocriticism, there is a perplexing connection between the concepts of development and sustainability. In postcolonial environmental studies, the idea of 'development' is analysed in terms of 'economic growth'. According to Wolfgang Sachs, proponents of development ideology use sustainable development as a new strategy to counter criticism of development's harmful effects (29). Like Wolfgang Sachs, Arturo Escobar argues that instead of addressing the social and environmental issues, sustainable development is the First World's most recent strategy to colonise the last areas of Third World social life" (198). In Mackay's novel, this has been represented through the speech of the President, who accused the climate activists of "undermining the national development plan" (Mackay76). The President's speech demonstrates that economic growth, rather than the environment, needs to be protected to achieve sustainable development.

However, in postcolonial environmental studies, it becomes a significant concern whether economic growth alone can ensure sustainable development in a climate-changed future, because "[t]here are no jobs if climate collapses; there is no food" (Mackay70). Moreover, if development truly facilitates the creation of a sustainable future, who will benefit from it? This is what has been fictionalised in Alistair Mackay's *It Doesn't Have to Be This Way*. In the novel, a nonlinear narrative technique is employed to address the causes and effects of climate change. The

novel has two narrative timelines set in the present and the future. In a future timeline in which climate change has ravaged the world, Cape Town is depicted as divided into two parts. The poor people confront climate catastrophes outside The Wall, while the wealthy and influential live a luxurious life within the climate-protected zone of the Citadel. Although Western ideology of development has generated a sustainable environment for the affluent citizens inside the Citadel, it has no positive impact on the lives of economically less powerful people, for whom it is “almost impossible to find food and water and shelter” (230).

Indigenous Environmentalism as a Form of Resistance to the Climate Crisis:

In his novel, Alistair Mackay portrays an ambivalent picture of the Western model of modern development through the characters of three queer friends: Luthando, Viwe, and Malcolm. In the novel, they meet at a reforestation festival. The depiction of these characters is used to trace the ecological damage done by the colonisers. The reference to “invasive alien species [that] acidified the soil” (Mackay11) suggests the ecological scars left by colonial rulers. Moreover, the statement that “there are no overhead leaves to intercept the rain” (11) illustrates how colonial practices, in the name of modern development, led to deforestation, which in turn has accelerated the current climate crisis. This articulates a connection between colonialism and the present planetary crisis of climate change.

Hence, the reforestation campaign can be interpreted as a symbolic act of restoring indigenous environments from colonial degradation. The saplings, planted in the forest, represent a form of ecological resistance—an act that reclaims what was lost to the European colonisers. Luthando’s remark— “the white man laid waste to our forest, and now we must put it right” (Mackay12)—highlights the environmental damage that the European colonial mission of development had done in the colonies. In this sense, the reforestation campaign in the novel could be described as an “act

of decolonialisation” (12), an act that exposes the hollowness of the colonial discourse of development.

The colonial ideologies of development persist even after colonisers left their colonies. The continuation of the colonial authority through the discourse of developmentalism over the postcolonial nations is described as a form of neocolonialism. In his book *Neo-Colonialism: The Last Stage of Imperialism* (1965), Kwame Nkrumah introduced the concept of ‘Neo-colonialism’, arguing that although the former colonies are officially independent, their economic and political conditions are controlled by the former colonial powers (1). The former colonial powers and the new superpowers, such as the US, continue to exert influence over the cultures and economies of third-world countries even after they attained political independence (Ashcroft et al. 178). The First World developed nations exert their authority over the developing nations through indirect means rather than direct military control. It indicates that colonialism has not yet ended. Instead, it has just changed its mode of domination over the developing nations. It highlights that:

Old-fashioned colonialism is by no means entirely abolished. It still constitutes ... Once a territory has become nominally independent it is no longer possible, as it was in the last century, to reverse the process. Existing colonies may linger on, but no new colonies will be created. In place of colonialism as the main instrument of imperialism we have today neo-colonialism. (Nkrumah1)

Though there are dissimilarities between colonialism and neocolonialism, their underlying ideology of establishing dominance over the colonised people remains the same, that is, the discourse of development.

Rather than abolishing traditional imperialism, contemporary development manifests it in novel forms, such as the persistent partnerships between national governments and colossal transnational corporations (Esteva 9-11). In this sense, the

economic and environmental exploitation of postcolonial developing nations is carried out not only by former colonial states but also by postcolonial governments that support transnational corporations in the name of national development. In Mackay's novel *It Doesn't Have to Be This Way*, Luthando and his fellow environmental activists conducted "peaceful protests"(98) to demand climate justice. However, these nonviolent efforts were ignored by the government and received no political attention. This indicates that political leaders in developing postcolonial nations replicate the actions of colonial rulers during the colonial period. Like the colonisers, these postcolonial governments are oblivious to the environmental damage that modern capitalist industries accelerate under the pretence of national development.

Moreover, the mimicry of the colonial model of development shapes the mindset of people in developing nations to such an extent that it is difficult for them to take climate change seriously. In the novel, Mackay depicts the escalating climate crisis and the political responses to it. The political preference for economic growth over ecological crisis is represented by juxtaposing two climatically catastrophic incidents: one in the present and the other in the past. In the past, Cape Town nearly ran out of water. In the novel, the Black South African character Luthando witnessed this disastrous situation as a child. Luthando "remembers the great drought that brought Cape Town to its knees... There were headlines all over the world about Cape Town: the first major city to succumb to the ravages of climate change" (Mackay55). Luthando's childhood experience of the climate crisis leads him to anticipate recurring water scarcity in the present. However, the South African government downplays the severity of the drought to maintain the city's economic growth. The municipal authorities are aware of the national economic damage, particularly the commercial decline of the tourism industry, resulting from 'Day Zero', a government-led strategy implemented in the past to address the water shortage crisis. The government's reluctance to acknowledge the severity of the crisis highlights the ambivalent relationship between national

development and environmental sustainability in postcolonial nations. Despite being vulnerable to climate change, postcolonial developing nations adhere to the Western development paradigm that prioritises short-term economic expansion at the expense of long-term environmental sustainability.

Mackay's *It Doesn't Have to Be This Way* illustrates how the pursuit of economic growth, understood as essential to the national development of postcolonial nations, often supplants climate resilience. The statement "you do not get economic growth by placing grey-water buckets in the fancy hotel bathrooms" (Mackay55) illustrates how environmental sustainability is understood as antithetical to economic development in postcolonial nations.

Notably, in Bradley's novel, Luthando condemns the government's policies that prioritise the interests of powerful industrialists over environmental protection. He expresses frustration with political leaders who make "empty promises" (Mackay 97) about clean energy yet continue to rely on coal, thereby contributing to the worsening climate crisis. The political inaction on climate change prompts Luthando to start 'guerrilla gardening'. It is the act of establishing plantations in public or private places that belong to others. The term 'guerrilla' alludes to the absence of legal authorisation "to grow [plantation] in a given space—and this makes guerrilla gardening illegal in most cases" (Kuchta). The motivations for guerrilla gardening vary depending on the sociopolitical and personal preferences. According to Luthando, guerrilla gardening is "a public service,...To green the city. It provides oxygen and resilience against climate change" (Mackay50). In the novel, Mackay portrays Luthando's guerrilla gardening as a form of environmental resistance to capitalist expansion in the postcolonial context. However, all his efforts fail to elicit any political intervention in the ecological crisis. His failure in environmental activism reinforces postcolonial ambivalence towards economic development and environmental sustainability.

In fact, it is the capitalist exploitation of natural resources, driven by Western self-serving development theory, that has intensified the unsustainable conditions of people in developing nations worldwide. Nonetheless, development is not antithetical to sustainability. It is the capitalist ideology of development, focused on serving the interests of the wealthy, that must be replaced by 'post-development'. Post-development is a set of pragmatic approaches that reassess development at the grassroots levels. It confronts "the fundamental contradiction of global capitalism and economic growth with the goals of equity, empowerment and a sustainable environment" (Saunders17). Rather than rejecting development, a liberal view of it, as espoused by the Indian economist Amartya Sen, should be promoted. According to Sen, the principal objective of development is not to attain economic growth but to expand human freedom. Here, freedom refers to everybody's right to participate freely in the global market. However, the market is not intended to be a vehicle of self-interest but a tool for establishing social justice (Sen295). Hence, development is not only about economic growth but also about several socioeconomic and political factors that enhance ecological sustainability and preserve the quality of all life forms.

Conclusion:

Mackay's *It Doesn't Have to Be This Way* belongs to the genre of climate dystopia. However, to challenge utter pessimism, the author employs a distant futuristic setting as a tool of "defamiliarisation". Distant settings in the novel evoke readers' perception of the spatiotemporal dimensions of climate change by defamiliarising them with the realities of this planetary crisis within their familiar world. The authors defamiliarise the known world by depicting a post-apocalyptic future shaped by climate change. The fictionalization of climate crisis through a defamiliarised setting "makes [humanity] see the world anew, not as it is but as it could be; it shows the world in sharp focus to bring out conditions that exist already but which, as a result of [humanity's] dulled perception, [they] can no longer see" (Varsam

206). In fact, by employing the narratological device of the defamiliarised setting, Mackay draws readers' attention to humanity's relationship to the real world and asks whether they are making the right choice. Hence, it can be argued that the integration of dystopian elements into the novel's plot serves as a satire of Western capitalism that exacerbates the ongoing climate crisis.

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